

ASSESSMENT OF TRANSPEDICULAR SCREW FIXATION COMBINED WITH POSTERIOR INTERBODY FUSION USING CAGE IN THE TREATMENT OF LUMBAR SPONDYLOLISTHESIS

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Introduction

Spondylolisthesis, characterized by a defect in the vertebral body at the pars interarticularis, occurs when instability leads to the vertebral body shifting forward. This sagittal subluxation of one vertebra over another is a common form of intervertebral instability. The first recorded case was documented in 1772 by obstetrician Herbinaux, who described lumbosacral spondylolisthesis causing challenges in childbirth due to the forward displacement of L5 on the sacrum.

Spondylolisthesis can arise from various causes, including congenital, isthmic, degenerative, traumatic, pathological, or postoperative origins. Prevalence varies, with L5-S1 commonly affected in children and about 5% of adult men and 10% of adult women showing spondylolisthesis without pars defects.

Patients often present with lower back pain, neurological symptoms, and/or radicular complaints, most frequently affecting the L3-S1 vertebrae. Symptoms typically worsen with activities like repetitive extension or rotation, while resting offers relief.

Modern surgical approaches, such as bilateral posterolateral fusion (PLF), show an 81-100% fusion success rate and a 60-98% clinical success rate. This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of treating lumbar and lumbosacral spondylolisthesis using transpedicular screw fixation and posterior interbody fusion with cage insertion.

Materials and Methods

This prospective and retrospective study included 25 cases of lumbar spondylolisthesis treated at the Scientific and Practical Center of Neurosurgery of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Inclusion Criteria included patients aged 20–50 with confirmed spondylolisthesis who experienced severe low back pain, neurological deficits (motor, sensory, or sphincteric issues), and unresponsive symptoms after conservative treatment. Patient improvement was assessed pre- and post-operatively using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) for pain and the Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) for disability. VAS measurements evaluated low back pain in moving, standing, and sitting postures.

Exclusion Criteria involved patients under 20, those with less than three months of back pain, asymptomatic spondylolisthesis, Grade 5 spondylolisthesis, or congenital spinal deformities.

Data Collection included personal demographics, the onset and progression of illness, and other relevant medical history.

Results

This prospective and retrospective study included 25 lumbar spondylolisthesis cases treated at the Scientific and Practical Center of Neurosurgery of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Preoperative imaging, including static and dynamic X-rays, DEXA scans, CT, and MRI as

needed, was conducted to assess spine anatomy, fracture and canal dimensions, and neural compression. Most cases (76%) involved the L4-L5 level.

Radiographs confirmed fusion cage placement and transpedicular screw positioning, with interbody fusion at L4-L5 in 64% of cases, followed by L5-S1 in 12% and other levels. Preoperative VAS pain scores averaged 7.64, reduced to 3.52 one week postoperatively and 2.32 after six months, indicating substantial improvement. Fixation levels were predominantly L4-L5 (64%) and L3-L4-L5 (12%). Mean surgery time was 95.59 minutes, with an average hospital stay of 2.37 days.

ODI scores improved significantly, dropping from a preoperative mean of 52.16% to 13.92% postoperatively (6 months), with an overall improvement of 38.28% ($P < 0.001$).

The preoperative Young Adult T-score index ranged from 0.9 to 1.2, with a median of 0.4 ± 0.69 . Six months postoperatively, this range remained consistent, showing no statistically significant change compared to the preoperative score.

Most patients (92%) experienced no complications, with only one case (4%) of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) leak and one case (4%) of superficial wound infection. Mean blood loss was 480.0 ± 87.8 cc, ranging from 300 to 700 cc.

Regarding radiculopathy improvement, 9 patients (36%) showed good improvement, 8 (32%) showed fair improvement, 7 (28%) experienced great improvement, and one patient showed no improvement.

Discussion

Many cases of spondylolisthesis are asymptomatic. Despite differences in causes, age, sex, and pathology among various types of spondylolisthesis, common symptoms include back pain, radicular pain, neurogenic claudication, deformities such as kyphosis or scoliosis, and gait disturbance.

This study aimed to assess the effectiveness of posterior interbody fusion with cage and transpedicular screw fixation for lumbar and lumbosacral spondylolisthesis treatment. Among group A patients, the average age was 57.85 ± 5.49 years, and in group B, it was 56.55 ± 6.63 years. Females comprised a majority in both groups (70% in group A and 65% in group B), similar to findings by Ghogawala and Moussa, who also reported higher female prevalence in spondylolisthesis studies.

Our study population, ranging from 26 to 65 years, had a median age of 43.92 ± 9.94 years, with the most common age group being 18-40 years (52%). Females were predominant (60%), with a male-to-female ratio of 0.67:1. These results are consistent with Mowafy et al., who examined transpedicular fixation and interbody fusion techniques in spondylolisthesis cases, highlighting the female majority and similar age ranges among patients.

Conclusion

Surgical intervention is typically required for spondylolisthesis when conservative treatments prove ineffective. Transpedicular fixation combined with interbody fusion is an effective approach for managing spondylolisthesis, offering stability and neural decompression while minimizing neurological risks. Partial repositioning and decompression of affected nerves reduce the likelihood of complications. Future studies should focus on larger, multicenter trials with long-term follow-up to further validate these findings and enhance treatment protocols for spondylolisthesis management.

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